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Review Article

ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: CAUSES AND TREATMENT**¹Dr Saniya khakwani,²Dr Mohammad Waleed Bin Fawad,³Dr Maroofa Habib**^{1,2}MBBS, Yusra Medical and Dental College, Islamabad.³MBBS, Shalamar Medical and Dental College, Lahore.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

The most common cause of dementia is Alzheimer's disease, and this is something that has the ability to grow with the aging process. It is now among the most common diseases found in the elder population. Two hallmark pathologies classically define this neurodegenerative disease process: neurofibrillary tangles of hyperphosphorylated tau and β -amyloid plaque deposition. Its diagnosis depends upon several criteria, fluid and imaging biomarkers. Trials are underway to reduce the production and risk of this brain issue, but currently, the focus is on symptomatic therapy.

In this paper, the recent advances in the understanding of Alzheimer's disease, clinical evaluation, and treatment are discussed.

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INTRODUCTION:

Dementia is a syndrome that is characterized by a continuous decline of two or more cognitive domains like language, memory, personality, behavior, executive and visuospatial function. The decline in these cognitive domains adversely impacts the ability to carry out the daily activities of life. Alzheimer's disease (AD) so far is the main and most common reason for dementia around the globe constituting almost more than 80% of all the dementia diagnoses.¹

Although the most common diseases accountable for death in the world are stroke and CVD, but the proportion of deaths owing to AD is also growing up and has reached 87% between 2000 to 2017. The direct and indirect annual costs of healthcare-related to AD is about \$600 billion.^{2,3} the definitive diagnosis is imperative for confirmation of the AD presence and it includes a post mortem evaluation of brain tissue via positron emission tomography (PET) biomarkers and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in combination with multiple other clinical procedures in living patients.⁴

At present, treatments like cholinesterase inhibitors at any AD stage of dementia and memantine for moderate to severe Alzheimer's disease dementia, are available for the patients. These medications do not change the course of the disease or the decline rate, however, these are found helpful in improving the quality of life for the patient as well as for their caregiver.^{5,6}

Epidemiology

In dementia, mild cognitive impairment may depict a transitional stage of the normal aging process to the early disease presence. The most common subtype of MCI (mild cognitive impairment), is amnesic MCI. It is defined as follows:

- Objective corroboration and a memory complaint
- Abnormal memory functions regarding age and education
- Normal daily activities of life
- Absence of dementia
- Intact general cognition⁷

The MCI has other subtypes as well, it includes MCI single domain non-memory, multiple domains MCI. These conditions require the impairment in at least one of the cognitive domains of non-memory sections such as executive functioning, language, or intact functioning.⁸ All MCI subtypes increase the risk of AD and other dementias. When it comes to the prevalence of MCI in non-demented elders the chances were found as 16% with an annual variable rate to dementia from 6% to 15%.⁹ MCI is quite heterogenous, although it is associated with a

high risk of dementia but in many cases, it remains stable or even reverts to the normal state.¹⁰

Causes of Alzheimer's Disease and Risk Factors

Alzheimer's is caused by the death of cells in the brain. It is a neurodegenerative disease which means that cell death continues to happen over time in the brain. In patients, with Alzheimer's disease, the tissues face connectivity issues and have fewer and fewer nerve cells and connections.

Autopsies have shown that plaques and tangles build up which appears as tiny deposits upon the nerve tissues in the brain in Alzheimer's. These plaques are made from a protein known as beta-amyloid and are found between the dying brain cells. The tangles form up between the nerve cells from another type of protein called tau. Exact causes of these changes are not known by many factors that are considered responsible for triggering these changes in the patient.¹¹

The Alzheimer's Association has enumerated the following risk factors after deep research.

➤ Risk Factors

The unavoidable risk factors, that can't be modified for developing the condition are as follows:

- Aging
 - A family history of Alzheimer's
 - Presence of certain genes
- The factors that are responsible for increasing the risk of the disease are:
- Severe/ undergoing or repeated brain injuries
 - Exposure to some harmful pollutant like toxic metals in the environment, pesticides and industrial chemicals

The modifiable factors that may aid in preventing the disease are as follows:

- Regular exercise
- Maintaining a healthy cardiovascular system
- Carefully managing CVD, diabetes, smoking, obesity and high blood pressure
- Consuming a healthy diet
- Indulgent in cognitive training and lifelong learning

It is also found that socially and mentally engaging activities play a very positive role in reducing the risk of Alzheimer's development.

Evolution of Alzheimer's Treatment

In 2011, the Aging Alzheimer's Association (NIA-AA) revised the clinical criteria for the MCI diagnosis and stages of dementia due to AD. The supportive biomarker evidence like imaging, serum, and CSF of AD pathology was added to aid the diagnosis of the disease. The change introduced by the NIA-AA encompassed geriatric cognitive, amnesic, delirium, dementia, and other disorders, and it also aided to discriminate the difference between neurodegenerative diseases like dementia,

AD with Lewy bodies, frontotemporal dementia, and major neurocognitive disorders. ¹²

The recent development of non-invasive diagnostic imaging has helped a lot in efficient and accurate AD diagnoses. Radiolabeled tracer agents are injected into the patients, after injection they went through a specialized PET scan that detects the plaques and deposition of amyloid- β peptides into these plaques in the brain. In 2012, clinicians succeeded in accurate diagnosis of the disease with 100% specificity and 96% sensitivity. ¹³ Now the list of imaging (amyloid specific PET ligands) has increased successfully and includes florbetaben, florbetapir, and flutemetamol. However, amyloid PET imaging is still limited because of its high cost, as not all of them can afford it.

A better invasive and less costly technique includes an examination of CSF for total tau protein, hyperphosphorylated tau peptide (p-tau), and A β 42 content. This method is less accurate as compared to the other ones mentioned before. Less invasive serum assays are under process, these are designed to measure the quantity of regulating protein implicated in AD. ¹⁴

Current Treatment

Currently, only two pharmacological therapies are available for patients with Alzheimer's disease. The cholinesterase inhibitors donepezil, galantamine, and rivastigmine for patients with moderate, mild, or severe Alzheimer's Dementia as well as for patients with Parkinson's disease dementia. Second therapy, known as memantine, has dual activities as a non-competitive N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor antagonist and as a dopamine agonist. The later therapy is for patients with moderate to severe AD who have difficulty with alertness and attention. Patients who go for alternative therapy, the nutraceutical huperzine A, showed an improvement in their memory functioning and activities of daily routine. ¹⁵

Deficiency of Vitamin D was also found as an independent risk factor for dementia development and its supplements are given to patients in which it is diagnosed. Many retrospective studies also revealed the role of inflammation in Alzheimer's disease development. It was found that the use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs reduced this risk to some extent. Two recent controlled, randomized, and double-blinded studies showed that omega-3 fatty acid supplements including fish oil played a significant role in improving memory and thinking capacity of patients with MCI.

Finally, the management of various diseases like CVD also contributed as a risk factor in overall brain health and was found associated with the cerebrovascular and neurodegenerative diseases.

People who adhere to the Mediterranean diet, including balanced portions of whole grains, olive oil, seafood, legumes, limited dairy, and poultry products, avoiding sweets, processed foods, and red meat, have reduced risk of developing Alzheimer's disease and cognitive decline. Moreover, regular exercise is also known for preventing metabolic conditions like diabetes mellitus and coronary artery diseases. ¹⁶ Physical activities, specifically exercise, prevents loss of strength and agility in patients with the growing age, and it also reduces neuropsychiatric symptoms linked with these brain issues. Recreational activities, like mind games, social tasks, and social collaboration are found to increase cognitive functions in elder life. Patients who exercised regularly, despite the presence of the genetic history of Alzheimer's disease, showed less atrophy in their brains.

• Anti-amyloid

According to the cascade amyloid hypothesis, the earliest manifestation of the disease is toxic plaques. It was found that these plaques induce the phosphorylation of tau protein at the onset of the symptoms. These plaques can spread like an infection via microtubules and transport to neighboring neurons causing neural death. On the basis of this evidence, a class of medicine is developed; monoclonal antibodies (passive immunotherapy). This includes an injection of antibodies that targets the A β and aids in their removal from the brain. Two such antibodies were initially developed in 2014, but the clinical trials showed that these medicines only work when administered in the early stages of MCI and mild dementia. Patients with moderate to severe AD dementia didn't show any improvement in cognitive scores. ¹⁷

Another approach to decrease the toxic plaque burden in the brain includes the inhibition or blocking of enzymes that produce A β peptide from the amyloid precursor protein. Currently, multiple drugs which target the (BACE1) β -site APP cleaving enzyme 1, are under examination. The novel agent verubecestat have achieved up to 40 fold reduction in A β levels in the brain of primates and rodents, on the basis of which the safe trials are expected in humans. While there are many drugs still under trial, the main focus of the researchers is on various approaches to eliminate or significantly reduce the A β levels, as it leads to success in Alzheimer's disease treatment.

• Anti-tau

Drugs are used to reduce the burden of this p-tau protein in the brain, as it is associated with the progressive AD and dementia in the patients. The potential treatments that are currently under clinical investigation and trials include, APP, amyloid precursor protein; p-tau, hyperphosphorylated tau peptide; BACE1, β -site amyloid precursor protein

cleaving enzyme 1; RAGE, the receptor for advanced glycation end products.¹⁸

CONCLUSION:

Alzheimer's disease is the main cause of dementia in the elder population. The successive treatment relies only upon the early (starting stages), efficient, and sensitive diagnosis of AD. The treatment options, currently underuse, which are supportive and symptomatic without attenuation of the prognosis are mainly two; cholinesterase inhibitors and memantine. These improve memory and alertness without affecting life expectancy or AD progression rate. Lifestyle modification is also an important preventive factor and improving factor for AD patients.

The two main pathological features, A β , and p-tau, associated with AD are currently the main targets of the clinicians for potential treatment. However, many drugs are under trials and the process is ongoing to develop effective means for early diagnosis and successful treatment.

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